

PSYCHOLOGICAL DIFFERENCES IN THE FORMATION OF IDEAS ABOUT THE FAMILY IN STUDENTS

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Annotation. This article discusses the influence of students' ideas about the family on the strength of the family and its psychological significance.

Keywords: family, parents and children, husband and wife, communication, society.

By family relations, we mean a socio-psychologically specific group relationship, that is, the process of communication between close relatives. This includes, first of all, communication between parents and children, husband and wife, mother-in-law and daughter-in-law, and similar family members. It is known from historical life experiences that one of the most delicate and controversial issues in the family is the relationship between mother-in-law and daughter-in-law.

The family is the support of the state and society, and perhaps even its main foundation.

Every state and society, striving for a healthy lifestyle, first of all sees this issue in the image of the family. From this perspective, today the institution of the family is not only a guarantee of stability of society, but also a factor ensuring its future prospects. It is necessary to recognize its sanctity, ensure its inviolability, and approach it from the perspective of the human factor, as the first vital necessity in the consciousness and thinking of every person, in the type of activity, and in emotional relationships. We will approach the issue correctly if we say that the stability of the socio-psychological environment in the family largely depends on the level of organization of the mother-in-law and daughter-in-law relations. When we study this issue scientifically, it becomes clear that the sacred institution of the family is precisely the character traits and worldview of people who perform this functional role of mother-in-law and daughter-in-law, creating a healthy or unhealthy environment. Today, certain conflicting relationships and unhealthy psychological environments in the families of our society are reflected in the dialogues of mother-in-law and daughter-in-law. As a result, conflicts arise between family members, and the fate of the so-called sacred family institution is increasingly under threat.

In a word, it can be said that one of the socio-psychological factors that cause the breakdown of families is precisely the conflict in the relationship between mother-in-law and daughter-in-law. Our national values, saturated with religious knowledge, have instilled in us from generation to generation that the role of parents and father-in-law in the family is incomparable.

Today, issues that call for reflection are on the agenda. Why is it that in previous times, a mother-in-law lived in harmony with several daughters-in-law in the family, but now even one daughter-in-law and her mother-in-law are being tormented by conflicting relationships? During this period, all the daughters-in-law were obedient and respectful to their mother-in-law, while at the same time, the only daughter-in-law is doing the opposite.

If we look at the issue from this perspective, we can observe the emergence of a superficial way of thinking among young people, a lack of sufficient psychological knowledge and understanding of the sanctity of the family, a lack of religious knowledge, and in particular, a poor approach to the rules of Sharia and moral norms.

Explaining the main factor that undermines the relationship between mother-in-law and daughter-in-law with these factors reveals the same truth. There is another side to this issue, which is external interference in the family, including the relationship between husband and wife, the mother-in-law's criticism of the son-in-law's positive attitude towards his wife, and the existence of pathological approaches in some families, which lead to the son's "anger" towards the daughter-in-law. As a result, the mother-in-law develops a feeling of hostility towards the daughter-in-law, treats her incorrectly, finds fault with her every move, and undermines the mother's nature.

Today, we all know that a number of programs and projects are being developed to prepare young people for the family. A number of roundtable discussions and mass television programs are being presented to the general public in an exemplary manner. Of course, this is a commendable issue. However, recognizing a bitter truth and looking at this issue from a psychological perspective is being ignored by experts. Regarding the need to conduct scientific research on problematic issues in family relations based on the needs of the time, representatives of the field J. Usarov, N. Eshnaev, T. Maratov touched upon this issue and said: "In our country, large-scale spiritual and educational events are being organized and socio-political programs are being developed to strengthen the family, identify and eliminate problems related to the family, especially to support young families. However, the increasing number of family separations requires a new approach to work in this area, and, moreover, scientific research." In this regard, we would like to express our opinion on the lack of a comprehensive psychological approach to the attitude of new brides to the owners of the house. An indifferent approach to this issue can create a socio-psychological environment that can lead to conflict situations not only in the relationship between the mother-in-law and the daughter-in-law, but also with family members at any time. It would be appropriate to consider that just as becoming a bride is every girl's dream, the inner anxiety about entering another household and adapting to the socio-psychological environment in it outweighs everything else.

Do we have any knowledge and understanding of this issue? Are we taking into account the strong mental state of the new bride? Are we creating appropriate conditions for her adaptation process? What effective psychological approach are we taking to alleviate her strong depression?

How much time does it take to learn a new environment, different people, different characters, and find a balanced point of relationship with them? Has any expert spoken about the fact that this situation can cause intense hidden stress in brides, making them nervous, having difficulty controlling themselves, and ultimately making uncontrollable mistakes or missteps? No!

Has any guidance been developed in this regard? No! Do the owners of the house where the new bride is staying have sufficient knowledge and understanding on this issue? No! Perhaps it is time to clarify the issue.

Simply put, we think it is appropriate to explain this issue figuratively. Think about it: the bride is a young sprout, and the house where the bride goes is the ground where she needs to grow?

In order for the beautiful sprout to take root and bear fruit, should the sprout itself be cultivated or should the ground be prepared thoroughly?

Of course, the ground! In conclusion, we can see that our activities are ineffective due to the one-sided and biased study of mother-in-law-daughter-in-law relations.

Considering that this issue needs to be studied more broadly and comprehensively, we put forward the following proposals: - Conduct psychotraining with future brides-to-be on adapting to the new environment before the wedding; - Create modern popular training manuals for mothers-in-law based on the recommendations and suggestions of psychologists on eliminating internal anxiety and depression in future brides-to-be; - Establish the relationship of the bride's family with the bride based on psychological factors; - Organize a school for future mothers-in-law and develop a targeted program for providing psychological knowledge; - Create a healthy psychological environment for brides-to-be to quickly adapt to a new home; - Closely familiarize the general public with propaganda and agitation that this issue is the main factor causing conflict in the relationship between mother-in-law and daughter-in-law; - Regularly disseminate the recommendations and suggestions of psychologists through the media, without abandoning roundtable discussions on this issue. - to abandon the use of singers, actresses, and representatives of the film and art world to express their opinions on family relations through the media, and to convey only the opinions of psychologists to the general public; - it is necessary to increase the literacy of journalists in this regard (who have forgotten that there are family psychologists and sociologists in our society) and properly educate their colleagues.

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